

Balancing Fairness and Accuracy Using Grammatical Evolution

Zahid Irfan¹[0000-0001-5719-3729], Róisín Loughran¹[0000-0002-0974-7106],
Muhammad Adil Raja¹[0000-0003-4666-7022], and Fergal
McCaffery¹[0000-0002-0839-8362]

Regulated Software Research Center (RSRC), Dundalk Institute of Technology
(DkIT), Dundalk, Co. Louth, Ireland
zahid.irfan, roisin.loughran, adil.raja, fergal.mccaffery @dkit.ie

Abstract. Balancing predictive accuracy and fairness in machine learning is a critical challenge. In this work we explore Grammatical Evolution (GE) for learning causal graphs and applying interventions to improve interpretability, while maintaining fairness of the machine learning models. We focus on the Equalized Odds Difference (EOD) metric to evaluate fairness across different datasets, including the German Credit, COMPAS, and Adult datasets. The results demonstrate that GE can effectively learn causal structures that enhance fairness while maintaining competitive accuracy compared to baseline methods. Additionally, we introduce fitness functions GE- α , GE- β , and GE- γ . GE- α uses constraints to ensure fairness and accuracy are at an optimum level. GE- β employs a Minimax strategy that jointly minimizes unfairness and 1-accuracy, ensuring balanced performance by reducing the worst-case metric, and GE- γ uses Average Causal Effect (ACE) based node dropping to enhance interpretability without compromising fairness and accuracy. Results demonstrate that the choice of fitness function significantly shapes the fairness-accuracy trade-off and GE can produce models with improved fairness while maintaining competitive accuracy.

Keywords: Genetic Algorithms · Grammatical Evolution · Fairness in Machine Learning · Responsible AI · Causal Interventions

1 Introduction

The deployment of Machine Learning (ML) systems in high-stakes domains such as healthcare, finance, and criminal justice has raised significant concerns regarding fairness and bias [4]. Biases from various sources like training data can lead to discriminatory outcomes, disproportionately affecting marginalized groups. Addressing these issues is crucial to ensure equitable treatment and prevent harm using different mitigation techniques [18]. Various fairness metrics have been

proposed to quantify and mitigate bias in ML models, including demographic parity, Equalized Odds Difference (EOD), and predictive parity [15]. In Section 2 related work is presented. Section 3 we describe the methodology, including the datasets used, performance metrics, and the calculation of Average Causal Effect (ACE). Section 4 outlines the benchmark methods employed for comparison. Section 5 details of the proposed Grammatical Evolution Framework. Section 6 presents the experimental results and Section 7 concludes with a summary of findings and future research directions.

2 Related Work

Directed Acyclic Graphs (DAGs) are powerful tools for representing relationships between variables in complex systems. In the context of ML, DAGs can be used as structure graphs to represent the relationships between features and outcomes. Bayesian Networks (BNs), which are built upon DAGs, allow for probabilistic inference and can be used to make predictions based on the learned structure [12,19]. Many existing graph discovery methods, such as the PC algorithm [21], Non-combinatorial Optimization via Trace Exponential and Augmented lagRangian for Structure learning (NOTEARS) [23], and Graphical Equivalence Search [5], face several significant challenges. First, these methods often exhibit instability, meaning that small changes in the input data can lead to substantially different learned graph structures, which undermines the reliability of the results. Second, they tend to have high computational complexity, making them inefficient and sometimes impractical for large-scale datasets or real-world applications. Finally, the graphs produced by these algorithms are frequently highly complex and difficult to interpret as shown by example in Fig. 1, which limits their usefulness in domains where model transparency and explainability are essential [14]. As a result, there is a need for approaches that can produce stable, computationally efficient, and interpretable causal graphs. In our earlier work

Fig. 1: DAG for German Dataset [17]

[15], we employed Grammatical Evolution (GE) to automatically generate struc-

ture graphs using context-free grammar. These structure graphs were then used to learn BN from the data, which enabled the models to make predictions. A key component in this approach was the balancing fairness and accuracy using fitness functions within the evolutionary process. By explicitly defining these objectives, the fitness evaluation component of the algorithm played a central role: it assessed each candidate solution (i.e., each generated graph) based on how well it balanced fairness and predictive accuracy. This allowed the evolutionary search to prioritize and evolve graph structures that achieved optimal trade-offs between these two important criteria. Our focus is to build on this approach and enhance it with constrained optimization, minimax optimization, and, ultimately, causal intervention in order to achieve a balance between fairness and accuracy, while also developing explainable models.

3 Methodology

3.1 Performance Metrics

In this study, we focus on the EOD as a fairness metric. The EOD is a crucial measure in assessing fairness in ML models, particularly in sensitive domains. The EOD measures the absolute difference in both True Positive Rate (TPR) and False Positive Rate (FPR) between the privileged and unprivileged groups, as introduced by Hardt et al [13]. EOD requires that both TPR and FPR are similar across groups, ensuring that the model’s predictions are equally accurate and fair for all. Formally, EOD is defined as:

$$\text{EOD} = \max \left(|\text{TPR}_{\text{priv}} - \text{TPR}_{\text{unpriv}}|, \quad |\text{FPR}_{\text{priv}} - \text{FPR}_{\text{unpriv}}| \right) \quad (1)$$

where $\text{TPR} = \frac{\text{TP}}{\text{TP} + \text{FN}}$ and $\text{FPR} = \frac{\text{FP}}{\text{FP} + \text{TN}}$ for each group, with TP, FP, TN, and FN denoting True Positives (TPs), False Positives (FPs), True Negatives (TNs), and False Negatives (FNs), respectively.

Accuracy is assessed by the proportion of correct predictions made by the ML model [12]. It is calculated as:

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{\text{TP} + \text{TN}}{\text{TP} + \text{TN} + \text{FP} + \text{FN}} \quad (2)$$

3.2 Average Causal Effect (ACE)

The ACE is a measure of the impact of a treatment or intervention on an outcome variable, averaged over a population. It is defined as the difference in expected outcomes between the treated and untreated groups. The ACE is calculated as follows:

$$\text{ACE}_{X \rightarrow Y} = \mathbb{E}[Y \mid \text{do}(X = x_1)] - \mathbb{E}[Y \mid \text{do}(X = x_0)] \quad (3)$$

where Y is the outcome variable, X is the treatment variable, and x_1 and x_0 represent the treated and untreated states, respectively. The ACE provides a quantitative measure of the causal effect of the treatment on the outcome, allowing for comparisons between different interventions or treatments [19]. Since ACE can be used to assess the impact of a feature on the target outcome, it can help to identify features that contribute to fairness disparities and can guide the design of interventions to improve fairness in ML models. The ACE is particularly useful in understanding the causal relationships between features and outcomes, enabling researchers to make informed decisions about interventions that can enhance fairness in predictive models [16].

3.3 Datasets

In this study, we use three datasets popular in the fairness domain. The German Credit dataset [11] consists of 1,000 instances with 20 mixed numerical and categorical features and exhibits class imbalance, with roughly 70% labeled as “good credit” and 30% as “bad credit”. The Correctional Offender Management Profiling for Alternative Sanctions (COMPAS) dataset, derived from risk assessment scores used in the U.S. criminal justice system, is widely studied for its inherent biases and fairness challenges, particularly regarding racial disparities in recidivism prediction [2]. COMPAS has balanced target classes. The Adult dataset (also known as the Census Income dataset) contains over 32,000 examples with demographic and employment attributes, and is a standard benchmark for income prediction tasks and fairness research [10]. The Adult dataset has 70% of instances with income less than or equal to 50K and 30% with income greater than 50K.

4 Benchmark Methods

The benchmark methods were selected to provide a comprehensive and diverse comparison across fairness-aware learning, causal discovery, and standard predictive modeling. This combination ensures that we compare our approach not only against domain-relevant baselines but also against strong fairness-focused and causal inference models.

4.1 Exponentiated Gradient Reduction

Fairlearn is a Python library that provides tools for assessing and mitigating fairness issues in ML models. It offers various algorithms and metrics to evaluate fairness across different groups, ensuring that models are fair and unbiased [22,1]. Fairlearn’s Exponentiated Gradient Reduction (EGR) method iteratively learns a randomized classifier by updating weights over different constraints to minimize fairness violations while controlling classification error. It serves as a representative method for algorithmic fairness mitigation.

4.2 Causal Discovery Using the Peter-Clark Algorithm

The Peter-Clark Algorithm (PC) algorithm is a well-established method for causal structure learning, allowing us to evaluate how explicitly modeling causal dependencies affects fairness and performance [21]. We use it to learn a structure graph from data, which is then used to build a BN for prediction. From these predictions, we compute both accuracy and the EOD fairness metric. Our implementation follows the stable variant proposed in [6], as available in the `pgmpy` library [3]. As a constraint-based method, PC identifies conditional independence relationships in the data to construct a DAG that captures the underlying causal structure. Its efficiency and scalability make it well-suited for our analysis. The structure graph for Adult dataset [10] is shown in Fig. 2, the target node is filled.

Fig. 2: Causal Structure Learnt by PC Algorithm for Adult Dataset, target node is filled

4.3 Logistic Regression

Logistic Regression (LR) is a widely used ML model for binary classification tasks due to its simplicity and interpretability [7]. In this study, we use LR as a baseline method to evaluate predictive performance. Both EOD and accuracy are employed to assess the model, providing a balanced view of its effectiveness and fairness across different groups.

5 Grammatical Evolution Framework

GE is a grammar-based Evolutionary Algorithm (EA) that evolves structured representations, such as mathematical expressions, models, or graph topologies, by mapping linear genotypes to phenotypes defined by a user-specified grammar. Unlike traditional Genetic Programming (GP), GE leverages formal grammars (typically in Backus Normal Form (BNF)) to ensure syntactic correctness and

domain-specific structure, offering high flexibility and adaptability in model development across diverse problem domains [20]. Fig. 3, shows the GE framework detailing various aspects like initializing population, genotype to phenotype mapping, evaluation, selection, crossover / mutation and replacement.

GE uses a context-free grammar to define the search space for evolutionary algorithms. The grammar is typically specified in BNF, which consists of production rules that describe how to generate valid structures (phenotypes) from linear representations (genotypes). The datasets were used to write grammar rules for generating structure graphs as follows:

1. $\text{edges} ::= \text{edge} \mid (\text{edge}, \text{edges})$
2. $\text{edge} ::= (\text{feature}, \text{feature}) \mid (\text{feature}, \text{class})$
3. $\text{feature} ::= \text{unprivileged_feature} \mid \text{privileged_feature}$
4. $\text{unprivileged_feature} ::= \text{first_feature} \mid \text{second_feature} \mid \dots$
5. $\text{privileged_feature} ::= \text{protected_feature} \mid \text{protected_feature2}$
6. $\text{class} ::= \text{target}$

Fig. 3: Grammatical Evolution

The present study concentrates on fitness functions that aim to improve both fairness and accuracy in ML models by utilizing GE. We propose three fitness functions for assessing individuals generated by GE, namely $\text{GE-}\alpha$, $\text{GE-}\beta$, and $\text{GE-}\gamma$. Each function incorporates a different mechanism to guide the search process and assess model quality.

Let the following be defined:

\mathcal{H} : Hypothesis space (set of classifiers)

$h \in \mathcal{H}$: A binary classifier

\mathcal{D} : Distribution over features X , sensitive attribute $A \in \{0, 1\}$,
and label $Y \in \{0, 1\}$

$\ell(h(X), Y)$: Prediction loss (e.g., 0–1 loss or a surrogate loss)

Define group-conditional rates:

$$\text{TPR}_a(h) = \mathbb{P}(h(X) = 1 \mid A = a, Y = 1), \quad \text{FPR}_a(h) = \mathbb{P}(h(X) = 1 \mid A = a, Y = 0)$$

$$\text{EOD} : \Delta_{\text{EO}}(h) = \max \{ |\text{TPR}_0(h) - \text{TPR}_1(h)|, |\text{FPR}_0(h) - \text{FPR}_1(h)| \}$$

5.1 Constrained Grammatical Evolution (GE- α)

GE was used in [15], focuses on learning causal graphs, utilizes BNs for predictions, and employs the Non-dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm II (NSGA-II) algorithm [8] to jointly optimize fairness and accuracy. An improved version GE- α , a key enhancement is the use of the EOD as the fairness metric, rather than the Equal Opportunity Difference, which focused only on the TPR [13] and additional constraints are applied to promote both fairness and accuracy. We aim to minimize classification error subject to a fairness constraint based on EOD. Specifically, we solve:

$$\min_{h \in \mathcal{H}} \mathbb{E}_{(X,A,Y) \sim \mathcal{D}} [\ell(h(X), Y)] \quad \text{subject to} \quad \Delta_{EO}(h) \leq \epsilon$$

Here, $\epsilon \geq 0$ is the maximum allowable fairness violation. The constraint ensures that the classifier’s TPR and FPR are similar across groups defined by A . This ensures the classifier has sufficient coverage of positive cases.

5.2 Minimax Grammatical Evolution (GE- β)

GE- β is inspired by the Minimax fairness approach introduced by Diana et al. [9]. GE- β jointly optimizes for fairness and accuracy by minimizing the worst-case trade-off between them, using the maximum of EOD and classification error as the optimization criterion.

$$\min_{h \in \mathcal{H}} \max \left(L_{\text{acc}}(h), L_{\text{fair}}(h) \right),$$

where $L_{\text{acc}}(h) = 1 - \text{Accuracy}(h)$, $L_{\text{fair}}(h) = \Delta_{EO}(h)$.

5.3 Grammatical Evolution with Causal Interventions (GE- γ)

This method extends GE- α by integrating the ACE metric to quantify the impact of interventions on fairness-related disparities. ACE is employed to identify features that causally contribute to observed fairness gaps and to guide the design of targeted interventions that mitigate these disparities in ML models. The population is modelled using a causal graph, where nodes represent features and edges encode causal relationships. Each individual corresponds to a specific instantiation of the variables within this shared causal structure. The ACE is computed for each feature to assess its influence on fairness outcomes. Features with low ACE values—indicating minimal causal impact—are pruned from the graph. This process facilitates the removal of causally irrelevant features, thereby enhancing the interpretability of the resulting models.

Let G be a directed acyclic graph (DAG) representing a causal Bayesian Network. We define two primary evaluation metrics: $\mathcal{F}(G)$: a fairness metric & $\mathcal{A}(G)$: model accuracy.

We define a multi-objective fitness function to minimize both fairness violation and error:

$$\min_G (\mathcal{F}(G), 1 - \mathcal{A}(G)) \tag{4}$$

Algorithm 1 GE- γ : Drop Low-ACE Nodes with Causal Role and Front-Door Checks

Require: Directed Acyclic Graph $G = (V, E)$, data \mathcal{D} , ACE threshold τ
Ensure: Modified graph G'

```

1: Initialize  $G' \leftarrow G$ 
2: for all node  $v \in V$  do
3:   Estimate ACE( $v$ ) using  $\mathcal{D}$ 
4:   if ACE( $v$ ) <  $\tau$  then
5:     if IsConfounder( $v, G$ ) or IsMediator( $v, G$ ) or IsCollider( $v, G$ ) then
6:       continue ▷ Preserve causal roles
7:     else
8:       Remove  $v$  and its incident edges from  $G'$ 
9:     end if
10:  end if
11: end for
12: return  $G'$ 

```

Let $\text{ACE}_G(v)$ denote the average causal effect of node v in graph G , and let τ be a predefined threshold. To ensure causal validity, we define structural roles for nodes and prevent removal of those that act as confounders, colliders, or mediators in the graph.

We define confounder, node v is a confounder for treatment T and outcome Y if:

$$\text{Conf}(v) \iff v \notin \text{Descendants}(T) \wedge v \text{ lies on a backdoor path from } T \text{ to } Y$$

Mediator, node v is a mediator if it lies on a directed path from T to Y , i.e.,

$$\text{Med}(v) \iff T \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow v \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow Y$$

Collider, a node v is a collider on a path $T \rightarrow v \leftarrow Y$, i.e., $\text{Col}(v) \iff \exists \text{ path } T \rightarrow v \leftarrow Y$

Then the pruned graph G' is defined as:

$$G' = G \setminus \{v \in V(G) \mid \text{ACE}_G(v) < \tau \wedge \neg \text{Conf}(v) \wedge \neg \text{Med}(v) \wedge \neg \text{Col}(v)\} \quad (5)$$

Optionally, a single-objective scalarization may be used:

$$\text{Fitness}(G') = \lambda \cdot \mathcal{F}(G') + (1 - \lambda) \cdot (1 - \mathcal{A}(G')) \quad (6)$$

where $\lambda \in [0, 1]$ is a trade-off parameter controlling the emphasis on fairness versus accuracy. The algorithm is formalized in Algorithm 1.

5.4 Threshold Selection

Let $\{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n\}$ denote the set of ACE values, and let $v_{(1)} \leq v_{(2)} \leq \dots \leq v_{(n)}$ be the sorted sequence. For a given percentile $p \in (0, 100)$, we define the threshold τ as

$$\tau = \text{Quantile}_p(\{v_i\}_{i=1}^n) = v_{(\lceil \frac{p}{100} \cdot n \rceil)}.$$

We conducted nodes pruning on the German dataset using different thresholds to evaluate the impact on fairness and accuracy. The results are summarized in Table 1. The table shows that as the threshold is greater than 0.1, the number of nodes pruned decreases, leading to a slight increase in fairness and accuracy. Therefore in our experiments, we set $p = 10$, so τ corresponds to the 10th percentile of ACE values.

Table 1: Thresholds used for node pruning in GE- γ for German Dataset.

Threshold	0.05	0.10	0.15	0.20
Nodes Pruned	12878	14767	10667	9727
Fairness	0.091	0.037	0.04	0.09
Accuracy	75%	73%	74%	78%

Table 2: Summary of Fairness and Accuracy Metrics across Datasets

Dataset	German		COMPAS		Adult	
Method	Accuracy	Fairness	Accuracy	Fairness	Accuracy	Fairness
EGR	75%	0.14	62%	0.08	80%	0.017
PC	74%	0.05	64%	0.16	82%	0.002
LR	74%	0.03	66%	0.32	84%	0.09
GE- α	79%	0.033	56%	0.019	83%	0.04
GE- β	79%	0.14	66%	0.27	84%	0.09
GE- γ	73%	0.037	57%	0.048	79%	0.025

6 Results and Discussion

The experimental results, summarized in Table 2, demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed methods in balancing fairness and accuracy across the three datasets. Each dataset presents unique challenges, and the performance of the methods varies accordingly.

The German dataset offers a moderate level of complexity with a moderately imbalanced distribution of classes and a mix of categorical and numerical features. The results in Table 2 indicate that the baseline methods show varying degrees of success in balancing accuracy and fairness. The EGR achieves similar accuracy but at the cost of a fairness gap. The PC algorithm, while slightly less accurate, demonstrates better fairness performance. LR provides a good balance. The proposed methods, particularly GE- α and GE- γ , outperform the baselines by achieving lower fairness gaps while maintaining competitive accuracy. This suggests that incorporating fairness constraints and causal interventions can lead to more equitable models without sacrificing predictive performance.

The COMPAS dataset is known for its inherent biases and challenges related to fairness, particularly in the context of criminal justice. The results in Table 2 highlight the difficulties faced by baseline methods in achieving both high accuracy and fairness. The EGR method, while achieving moderate accuracy, performs better on the fairness gap. The PC algorithm, although slightly more accurate, struggles with fairness disparities. LR, while accurate, shows fairness issues. The proposed methods demonstrate a marked improvement in fairness metrics, with GE- α achieving the lowest fairness gap among all methods. Although there is a slight trade-off in accuracy, the results indicate that targeted interventions can effectively mitigate biases present in the dataset, leading to fairer outcomes.

On the Adult dataset, the baselines already achieve strong performance, both in accuracy and fairness. For instance, PC reaches a fairness score of 0.002 while maintaining an accuracy of 82%, outperforming all of the proposed GE variants in terms of fairness. The GE methods, while competitive in accuracy (79% to 84%), show higher fairness violations ranging from 0.025 to 0.09. This outcome can be attributed to the large sample size and relatively balanced class distribution in Adult, where the baselines benefit from stable optimization and naturally low group disparities. In contrast, the GE family’s minimax-inspired formulations introduce a more conservative trade-off, prioritizing robustness over minimizing fairness metrics to their absolute lowest values. Although the fairness values of the GE methods may appear different from the baselines at first glance, these differences are not much considering their values are very low. This indicates that the GE family performs comparably well, achieving a balance between fairness and accuracy that is on par with the baselines. In other words, the proposed methods also provide effective and reliable solutions, offering fairness–accuracy trade-offs that are broadly similar to existing approaches. As an

Fig. 4: Adult Dataset: Best Graph with and without Pruning

example, Fig. 4 shows the best graph learnt for Adult dataset with and without pruning. The pruned graph is not only simpler and more interpretable. This is valuable because interpretability is often a major concern in fairness-aware ma-

chine learning: complex models can obscure the decision-making process, making it harder for practitioners, regulators, or stakeholders to trust and validate outcomes. The method provides a practical balance between performance, fairness, and transparency.

7 Conclusions and Future Work

While the baseline models demonstrate comparable performance, the GE variants consistently achieve more balanced outcomes because these objectives are part of the optimization. Another significant advantage is that the GE methods produce interpretable models in the form of causal graphs, which can be crucial for understanding and addressing fairness issues. The ability to visualize and interpret the learned structures provides insights into the relationships between features and their impact on fairness metrics. Additionally, we have many competing graphs that achieve similar performance, which can be useful for model selection based on other criteria such as interpretability or domain knowledge.

The results of these experiments suggest several avenues for future work. Refinement of the fitness functions could be investigated to enhance the balance between fairness and accuracy, exploring other causal inference techniques could provide deeper insights into mitigating biases in ML models, and applying these methods to other datasets and domains would help validate their generalizability and effectiveness in diverse contexts.

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